

1 **Playing with food - the effects of Augmented Reality on meal perceptions**

2 **Abstract**

3 Augmented reality (AR) has emerged as a key method of reducing the intangibility associated
4 with online shopping in and has seen research in fashion, cosmetics, furniture, but not in food
5 delivery, an industry worth \$150 billion globally. This study investigates how AR features such
6 as simulated physical control and environmental embedding influence cognitive (quality of
7 mental imagery), affective (ease of evaluation, product liking) and behavioural consumer
8 responses (purchase intention). A total of 503 participants took part in the study, revealing both
9 simulated physical control and environmental embedding to have influenced the ease of
10 evaluation, but not product liking. A mediation analysis between environmental embedding
11 and product liking with quality of mental imagery as a mediator, however, revealed a complete
12 mediation, allowing us to posit it as the reason for the indirect relationship between
13 environmental embedding and product liking. Ease of evaluation did not translate into purchase
14 intentions, although we did discover a strong influence on purchase intention from product
15 liking. This study provides several theoretical contributions contrary to extant AR research and
16 discusses the possible reasonings behind them such as the nature of the product and personal
17 preferences. It also contains takeaways for retailers, our thoughts on research limitations and
18 potential for further research.

19 **Keywords**

20 Augmented Reality, WebAR, Simulated Physical Control, Environmental Embedding, Quality
21 of Mental Imagery, Product Liking, Ease of Evaluation, Purchase Intention

22 **1.0 Introduction**

23 With online food delivery becoming worth more than \$150 billion globally, having
24 more than tripled since 2017 (Ahuja, Chandra, Lord, & Peens, 2021), and the actual process of
25 online purchasing providing emotional arousal and experiential value (Suhartanto, Helmi Ali,
26 Tan, Sjahroeddin, & Kusdibyoy, 2019; Yeo, Goh, & Rezaei, 2017), the creation of sensory

27 experiences has become pivotal to food retailers. The achievement of such superior experiences
28 via a radical transformation of the online environment, which Hoyer, Kroschke, Schmitt,
29 Kraume, and Shankar (2020) cite as essential in today's competitive environment, is only
30 possible if one can overcome the physical separation between them and the consumers. Adding
31 to the same is Petit, Velasco, and Spence (2019) who posits that the provision of sensory
32 information is more important than ever as it provides consumers with higher confidence in
33 their choices and increases purchase intentions. Online retailers attempt to do this via well-
34 designed, digitally-enhanced product presentations despite the issue of intangibility, which
35 Laroche, Yang, McDougall, and Bergeron (2005) cite as a pivotal factor in consumer decision-
36 making. This intangibility can be reduced if the products were presented in a medium such as
37 Augmented Reality (AR), as per the work of Heller, Chylinski, de Ruyter, Mahr, and Keeling
38 (2019b), who built on the concept of active inference to investigate how multi-sensory AR can
39 be used in e-retail. Our review of the extant literature on the use of AR in online food retail and
40 their impact on consumer behaviour, however, left much to be desired, revealing a research
41 gap, unlike on products such as furniture, clothing and makeup. Reiterating this is the latest
42 literature review on AR-induced consumer behaviour from Riar, Xi, Korbel, Zarnekow, and
43 Hamari (2022) who discovered only two AR articles related to food. Considering the
44 aforementioned growth of food delivery, this paper's first aim is to address this gap, heeding
45 the call for further research from Caboni and Pizzichini (2022) who discovered that COVID-
46 19 had accelerated the AR adoption in the fashion and beauty sectors, and urged future
47 researchers to extend it to other retail sectors such as food to provide more generalizable results.

48 Considered to be a construct revolving around its three dimensions: physical
49 intangibility, generality, and mental (Laroche, Bergeron, & Goutaland, 2001), intangibility
50 determines the cognitive, behavioural difficulty and effort a consumer would require to judge
51 and discriminate among alternatives and make a selection decision (Laroche et al., 2005).
52 Another impact of intangibility is its impact on consumer perception of risk (Eggert, 2006;
53 Laroche et al., 2005), which incidentally is a topic that has seen much research from academics
54 (Nepomuceno, Laroche, & Richard, 2014; Vinhal Nepomuceno, Laroche, Richard, & Eggert,
55 2012). Research revolving around the use of AR and the two most widely used antecedents of
56 perceived risk (Laroche et al., 2005): privacy and security concerns have therefore sprung up
57 (Feng & Xie, 2019; Harborth & Pape, 2021; Lebeck, Ruth, Kohno, & Roesner, 2018;
58 Rauschnabel, He, & Ro, 2018), raising many interesting findings. The same however cannot
59 be said for AR research concerning intangibility and evaluation difficulties as we discovered

60 in our review of extant literature as well as in that of the most recent retail-themed AR literature
61 reviews (Z. Du, J. Liu, & T. Wang, 2022; Kumar, 2022; Lavoye, Mero, & Tarkiainen, 2021;
62 Rejeb, Rejeb, & Treiblmaier, 2021). Such evaluation difficulties caused by overload, similarity
63 and ambiguity as per the work of V. W. Mitchell and Papavassiliou (1997), V. W. Mitchell and
64 Papavassiliou (1999), V.-W. Mitchell, Walsh, and Yamin (2005), can cause consumer
65 confusion. Considering Online shopper confusion is linked to negative behavioural reactions
66 (Garaus, 2018), our second research aim is to discover how food products presented in AR
67 helps with the ease of evaluation (EOE).

68 Another noticeable fact in our review of extant AR research was that a sizable number
69 of studies tended to be focused on its technological acceptance. As commendable as this is, one
70 must also consider that AR is no longer an emerging technology and has been tested among
71 consumers in a commercial capacity. Therefore, today's researchers should be more focused
72 on understanding the unique underlying psychological mechanisms that drive consumer
73 behavioral responses. This is all the more important as a closer look at the table presenting
74 prior research on AR in retailing, published in the recent work by Kowalczyk, Siepmann, and
75 Adler (2021), helped us to discover that there is a lack of research aiding comprehension of
76 how underlying affective and cognitive psychological mechanisms can drive behavioural
77 responses. The same is encouraged in the future research agenda of Zhao Du, Jun Liu, and
78 Tianjiao Wang (2022) who conducted a systematic literature review on AR research. While the
79 paucity in this research area has begun to be addressed in the work by Kowalczyk et al. (2021)
80 and Heller, Chylinski, de Ruyter, Mahr, and Keeling (2019a), our third research aim is to add
81 to this by investigating how AR products presentation impacts cognitive psychological
82 mechanisms such as quality of mental imagery (QMI), affective mechanisms such as EOE,
83 product liking (PL), and how they, in turn, impact a behavioural response such as purchase
84 intention (PI).

85 The outcome of our research makes several important initial contributions that we
86 expect to compound upon at the end of this manuscript. The first is that it helps reduce the gap
87 in consumer behaviour research in the AR and online food retail domain. The second is that it
88 is also the first to evaluate the impact of AR product presentation on a construct such as EOE.
89 The inclusion of this construct we feel is a valuable one, considering the importance of reducing
90 consumer confusion, and its impact on the overall shopping experience and purchasing
91 patterns. Research into this factor we believe will generate important findings for academics,
92 but also food retailers as the food a consumer order online is not usually returnable, which

93 means that the EOE is more important than if one was ordering a pair of shoes. The third is the
94 furthering of research on how AR drives cognitive and affective psychological mechanisms
95 and their impact on an important behavioural response such as PI. In doing so, we heed the call
96 to utilise new variables other than the more frequently tested constructs such as perceived
97 value, satisfaction, purchase and recommendation intentions, thereby unpicking decision
98 complexity, as recommended in the future research agenda of the AR literature review of
99 Hilken et al. (2018). The fourth is that our research was conducted with respondents in their
100 environment, unlike 50% of AR research that was done in a controlled laboratory setting,
101 thereby raising issues of the generalizability of consumer behaviour (Kumar, 2022) which
102 increases the psychological realism of research. Our research methodology, therefore, heeds
103 the call for results validated by real users from AR researchers such as H. K. Song, Baek, and
104 Choo (2020), Watson, Alexander, and Salavati (2020) and Xu, Zhang, Cui, and Yang (2020).
105 Another fact worthy of note is that ours is the first research to conduct e-retail research using a
106 WebAR, a technology that allows users to visit a website and place the 3D model in their
107 environment with the click of one button. This research opted for this technology as previous
108 research designs tasked respondents with downloading separate apps, such as IKEA and
109 Amazon Shopping App. Experiencing a product in AR in this manner requires users to expend
110 more effort, thus increasing effort expectancy, which, coincidentally, negatively affects PI
111 (Venkatesh, Thong, & Xu, 2012). The use of WebAR in this research might also be a nudge
112 for retailers, who have been hesitating to present their offerings in AR due to the costs involved
113 in building an app, as WebAR is a much cheaper option. Academics keen on furthering AR
114 research using other products such as we have done with food here might also consider using
115 WebAR due to the rather easy and cost-effective set-up.

116 **2. Conceptual background**

117 **2.1 Intangibility and its effects**

118 One of the core differentiators between when a customer would do their retail shopping
119 online and a bricks-and-mortar is the intangibility as per Laroche et al. (2005) who researched
120 intangibility and its consequences in Internet versus bricks-and-mortar retailers. This
121 intangibility or lack of physical evidence as per the same authors is a key influencer on the
122 perceived risk and evaluation difficulty, factors which are central to consumer evaluations and

123 purchasing behaviours. While more recent AR research has focused on the two most widely
124 used antecedents of perceived risk: privacy and security concerns (Cowan, Javornik, & Jiang,
125 2021; Harborth & Pape, 2021; Lammerding, Hilken, Mahr, & Heller, 2021; Rauschnabel et al.,
126 2018), there is scant research on AR's impact on the easing of evaluation difficulties, let alone
127 in the food domain. Such evaluation difficulties, as per McDougall (1987) are the perceptions
128 of the cognitive and behavioural difficulty and effort a consumer would require to judge and
129 discriminate among alternatives and make a decision. Put simply, it is the ease with which a
130 consumer can decide between alternatives and must not be confused with the concept of
131 decision comfort analysed in the AR research of H. K. Song et al. (2020) or Hilken, de Ruyter,
132 Chylinski, Mahr, and Keeling (2017), as it is the degree that consumers are satisfied and feel
133 at ease with a specific decision (Parker, Lehmann, & Xie, 2016).

134 A construct deserving of mention here is mental intangibility, the third dimension of
135 the concept of intangibility introduced by Laroche et al. (2001), alongside physical intangibility
136 and generality. Mental Intangibility as per the authors reflects the fact that a product can be
137 physically tangible, but difficult to grasp mentally. Adding to this are Nepomuceno, Laroche,
138 Richard, and Eggert (2012) who produce that mental intangibility is a deficiency in a
139 multisensory representation of a product. This inability to create a vivid correspondence
140 between the actual sensory experience of a real product found in a store and the mental
141 simulation of such an experience means that customers are required to expend higher
142 processing efforts (McDougall, 1987) and makes the evaluation more difficult (Laroche et al.,
143 2005). Considering that one of the major differences between physical and online retail
144 retailers, contributing to mental intangibility is the lack of a multisensory experience, our
145 research opts to adopt two multisensory constructs: simulated physical control (SPC) and
146 environmental embedding (EE).

147 SPC and EE are concepts drawn from the theory of situated cognition and first
148 introduced in the work of Hilken et al. (2017) who conducted research into the strategic
149 potential of AR to enhance online service experiences. According to this theory, consumers
150 can know more about an offering when the associated experience enables them to link abstract
151 "facts" with a real-time context (EE) and physical interaction (SPC). These two factors have
152 been used in recent AR research (Fan, Chai, Deng, & Dong, 2020; Huang, 2021; H. K. Song
153 et al., 2020) to evaluate their impact on decision comfort, willingness to pay more, but not in
154 the ease of evaluation (EOE). Concerning how the SPC can impact EOE, extant research on
155 the need for touch (NFT) and product evaluations reveals that those with a high NFT were less

156 confident of their evaluations with mounting frustration (Peck & Childers, 2003). Another
157 study worthy of note is that of Jiang and Benbasat (2004) who discovered that an electronic
158 interface where the user possesses functional control was discovered to increase perceived
159 diagnosticity, which is the degree to which a consumer believes the shopping experience is
160 helpful to evaluate a product. Related research on EE, however, has shown that customers prior
161 to purchasing a product not only visualise themselves trying the said product out but also use
162 their immediate environment to support such visualisation (Escalas, 2004). Adding to the same
163 is Hilken et al. (2017) who posits that the process of imaging how a product one is considering
164 purchasing would fit with the environment it is to be used in can be too taxing. Considering the
165 above, our research expects that the EE afforded by AR relieves the customer of this burden
166 and can provide more information about the product, thereby making its evaluation easier.

167 *H1. Simulated physical control positively influences ease of evaluation*

168 *H2. Environmental embedding positively influences ease of evaluation*

169 **2.2 Product liking**

170 Tangible product presentations put consumers more at ease when purchasing a product
171 online (Heller et al., 2019b) and are an important retail factor (Parker et al., 2016). This is all
172 the more important if the customers have a higher need for touch, as those with an autotelic
173 need for touch who experience pleasure simply by touching the product while those who with
174 an instrumental need for touch use it for evaluating the product's attributes, usefulness, and
175 quality (Gatter, Hüttl-Maack, & Rauschnabel, 2022). Extant research in this sphere is also of
176 the opinion that the simulation of a physical interaction using a touch screen through which a
177 customer can interact with a product may evoke affective reactions and improve customers'
178 ability to evaluate an offering (Brasel and Gips, 2014; Grohmann et al., 2007; Rosa and Malter,
179 2003). An important study to note here is that of de Vries, Jager, Tijssen, and Zandstra (2018)
180 who discovered meaningful interactions between touchscreen interfaces and high interactivity
181 images to have increased ownership feelings and subsequent product valuations across food
182 product types. Adding to work on the interactivity of products and consumer responses from
183 an AR perspective is Kowalczyk et al. (2021), who discovered the ability to interact with or
184 exert SPC on AR products to have influenced product liking positively. As product presentation
185 using AR increases the processing fluency of contextual products (Heller et al., 2019a), it is

186 also fair to infer that the same products can generate positive aesthetic responses from
187 consumers, as noted in the work by Reber, Schwarz, and Winkielman (2004). An analogous
188 relationship was discovered in the study by Winkielman and Cacioppo (2002) who, through
189 the use of facial electromyography (EMG), discovered that high processing fluency drives
190 positive affective responses, as was observed by increased activity over the region of the
191 zygomaticus major, the smiling muscle. Echoing the above is the work of Fan et al. (2020) who
192 discovered that the SPC and EE properties of AR retail products can reduce consumers’
193 cognitive load, enhance their cognitive fluency, and improve their product attitude.
194 Considering the above, we posit that

195 *H3. Simulated physical control positively influences product liking*

196 *H4. Environmental embedding positively influences product liking*

197 **2.3 Quality of mental imagery**

198 Defined as a “mental activity that visualizes a concept or relationship” by Lutz and Lutz
199 (1978) mental imagery, or the ability one has to imagine the use of products or experiences is
200 a pivotal skill when making consumer decisions (Pearson, Naselaris, Holmes, & Kosslyn,
201 2015). It is a multidimensional construct, with elaboration, which is the number of images
202 generated while processing the information and quality, the vividness of the images, taking
203 centerstage (Walters et al., 2007; Yoo and Kim, 2014). Bar (2007) produces that mental
204 imagery is useful as customers are in the habit of visually simulating the use of an offering so
205 that they may foresee the consequence of its usage to gain certainty about the product’s
206 attributes. Mental imagery is also crucial in information processing (Schlosser, 2003), drive
207 positive emotional responses to product presentations (Yoo & Kim, 2014) and helps explain
208 functional as well as hedonic consumption experiences (Rodríguez-Ardura and Martínez López
209 2014). Considering the evidence making the case for the important role of imagining a product’s
210 usage and purchasing decision, we concur with Bar (2007) and Heller et al. (2019a) that pre-
211 consumption evaluations and decision making would not be possible without it. Such mental
212 images as generated based on the subjective mental processes of an individual (Heller et al.,
213 2019a), and can be derived from visual, auditory, verbal or haptic stimuli, with visual being
214 the stimuli through which decision making and consumption are decided (Schifferstein, 2009).

215 Mental imagery is that it takes place in two stages: imagery generation, where the mental
216 images are generated from immediate perceptual information and integrated into a meaningful
217 context and imagery transformation, where the generated mental images are further
218 transformed (Kosslyn, Thompson, & Ganis, 2006; Pearson et al., 2015). These two stages as
219 per Kumar (2022) who conducted a systematic review and research agenda of AR in online
220 retailing, are easily met by the key affordances of AR: EE and SPC. Adding onto the same is
221 Heller et al. (2019a) who posits that imagery generation which is usually a memory-intensive
222 process, with the generated mental images subject to rapid decay, is no longer an issue for a
223 customer as with AR, they can embed a 3D model of the product into their backdrop. They
224 then posit that imagery transformation is handled by SPC as it can offload the memory intensive
225 task of transforming the generated mental images by spatial relocation. Considering the
226 importance of mental imagery, and AR's ability to drive both stages of mental imagery, we
227 consider it important to investigate how they impact the QMI. Recent AR research also seems
228 to mirror our opinion on the importance of such investigations as Park and Yoo (2020)
229 discovered that the controllability and playfulness of AR products significantly and positively
230 influenced the quality of mental images. The impact of environmental augmentation or EE, on
231 QMI however appears to be under-researched, prompting us to posit that

232 *H5. Simulated physical control positively influences the quality of mental imagery*

233 *H6. Environmental embedding positively influences the quality of mental imagery*

234 Miscalculated perceived value of offerings can lead to product returns, and
235 dissatisfaction with the purchase experience (S. Song & Kim, 2012) which could have been
236 avoided had the customer been able to view the products in AR and offload the mental imagery
237 processing while making the purchasing decision (Dror & Harnad, 2008; Heller et al., 2019a).
238 Adding to the same are Bone and Ellen (1992) who, in their advertising research, found
239 consumers who conjured more vivid mental imagery of a product to have a more positive
240 attitude towards it. This underlying process that mental imagery has on constructs such as EOE
241 and PL can be best explained by the availability-valence hypothesis, which produces that the
242 evaluation of a product is dependent on available information on it (Kisielius, 1982). Adding
243 to the same are MacInnis and Price (1987) who posits that the degree of mental imagery
244 influences the intensity of the emotion. From an AR perspective, an interesting study is that of
245 Park and Yoo (2020) who discovered that the QMI had a significant positive impact on the

246 attitude toward a product. Extant research on products presented on websites also discovered
247 that the QMI generated via a product drives positive emotions and behavioural intentions (Yoo
248 & Kim, 2014). Adding to the same is the work of Lee and Shin (2020) who discovered that
249 individuals who were able to generate high quality mental imagery were more likely to have
250 more positive attitudes towards the said product. Considering the above, we hypothesize that,

251 *H7. Quality of mental imagery positively influences ease of evaluation.*

252 *H8. Quality of mental imagery positively influences product liking.*

253 **2.4 Purchase intentions**

254 An increase in positive attitudes (PL), and a decrease in the effort needed to evaluate
255 between products (EOE), can translate into positive outcomes for retailers. An example of this
256 is discovered in the work of Kowalczyk et al. (2021) who analyzed the cognitive, affective,
257 and behavioural consumer responses to AR in e-commerce, and discovered that behavioural
258 responses such as PI were formed by the affective responses they analyzed of which PL was
259 one. Adding to the same is the research of Haile and Kang (2020) who discovered that a positive
260 affection for mobile AR can lead to an increase in consumers' PI. Another recent study worthy
261 of note is that of Tan, Chandukala, and Reddy (2021) who studied the impact of AR on sales
262 and discovered that it was most effective when product-related uncertainty is high,
263 demonstrating the technology's potential to increase sales by reducing uncertainty and
264 instilling purchase confidence. Despite the positive association between PL, EOE and PI above,
265 it is also worth remembering that food preferences are complex behaviours that are determined
266 by many factors and interactions (Köster, 2009), so a customer who ends up liking the product
267 might not choose to move forward with the actual purchase, due to a multitude of other reasons
268 outside the scope of this study. The authors however concur with the findings discovered in
269 extant research and posit the below and present our theoretical model in figure 1.

270 *H9. Product liking positively influences purchase intention.*

271 *H10. Ease of evaluation positively influences purchase intention.*

272 *Figure 1. Theoretical framework, author developed, 2022.*

273

274 3. Methodology

275 3.1. Materials

276 The key technology that allowed us to provide an AR experience on a website, without
 277 having to use an app, is WebAR - a revolutionary, new technology that allows smartphone
 278 users to display the product in their own space without needing to install additional applications
 279 (Graves, 2020). In addition to increasing the accessibility of AR, maintaining the development
 280 of the website under our control relieved us of concern about any well-known branding
 281 skewing our results, unlike in the case of such apps as those of IKEA, Sephora or L’Oreal. For
 282 this experiment, the website we developed contained only a single product page that allowed
 283 the product to be displayed in AR. The invited study respondents had only one task to
 284 experience the product in AR - to click on the "view product in your environment" button and
 285 point the rear camera of their mobile device towards a flat surface. In the trial, we used a high-
 286 quality 3D model scaled to the actual size of the actual product used to create it, thus increasing
 287 the sense of realism. In the planned experiment, we used a dish model (“Chicken Meal”),
 288 created by jjagdishwar (2020) on Sketchfab licensed under CC BY 4.0, as previous research
 289 on AR in the retail context was based on other products that required respondents to evaluate
 290 the product within a specific context. An example of this is how a consumer considering the

291 purchase of a t-shirt would be concerned about its ability to match well with what they are
292 wearing, the rest of their wardrobe and/or the accessories that can be worn with it. This context
293 would be more important if one was purchasing furniture which tends to be a higher investment
294 than a t-shirt. In the case of the fast consumable category of products such as food, what is
295 assessed is the food itself, which allows us to identify the importance of AR in its evaluation.

296 **3.2 Research procedure**

297 The study was explained to consumers in the online questionnaire. They were informed
298 that they would participate in the survey using their personal smartphone, that all data will be
299 de-identified and only reported in the aggregate. All participants acknowledged an informed
300 consent statement in order to participate in the study. First, a pilot study was carried out among
301 10 participants to check the possibility of experimenting with remote conditions due to
302 limitations resulting from the pandemic situation. This was carried out in the field of direct
303 research with the participation of respondents while maintaining the reliability and credibility
304 of the research. The study was performed using the mTurk platform, with full informed consent
305 from the respondents, who were aware of their right to leave the experiment at any stage. As a
306 result of preliminary research, it was decided to use a 2-step procedure. First, the participants
307 were asked to launch the website specified in the recommendation using a mobile device and
308 display the product in their own space using AR. The obligatory part of the task was to create
309 a screenshot of what the product superimposed onto their local environment appeared as,
310 allowing us to verify whether the participants had experienced the product in AR and whether
311 their responses to the questionnaire were related to the spatial presentation of the product.
312 Produced in figure 2 are examples of such screenshots taken by the authors of the study. In the
313 second part, the respondents, after becoming acquainted with the product, were asked to
314 participate in a questionnaire survey. Apart from questions about respondents, the
315 questionnaire consisted of statements to which the participants had to provide a response (on a
316 scale of 1-7, where: 1 –‘I strongly disagree’; 7 –‘ I definitely agree’). We implemented the
317 research by Song Hyo, Baek, and Choo Ho (2019), in which SPC was measured on 3 variables
318 and EE on 2 variables. QMI used 4 items, as proposed by Park and Yoo (2020). The work by
319 McDougall (1987) was used to test the EOE variable. In the case of PL, a 3-item scale from
320 the study by Kowalczyk et al. (2021) was utilised. The PI measurement was also based on 4
321 items from the work by Kowalczyk et al. (2021). The list of questions is provided in ‘Appendix

322 1'. The questionnaire also included 2 attention checking questions at random points to verify
323 respondents' attention, which allowed the elimination of unreliable responses.

324 *Figure 2.* Example of screenshots requested to verify responses. Photos captured by the author
325 smartphones, 2022.

326

327

328 3.3 Respondents

329 In total, 503 respondents took part in the study. In connection with the procedure
330 described in the previous section, 2-stage quality control of the obtained data was applied in
331 the study. From the entire group, 68 shared photos were disqualified because they did not
332 confirm that the product was displayed in AR. Additionally, 27 people failed the attention
333 checks, which were implemented to verify conscious reading of the questions (e.g. 'Please
334 select two for this question'). Therefore, answers obtained from 408 individuals were qualified
335 for the next part of the analysis. The mean age among this group of respondents was 32.16
336 years (SD = 8.72, minimum-18, maximum-71, n = 408). The group was diverse in terms of
337 gender, education level, income, and current professional situation. More information about
338 the demographics of the respondents is available in Table 1.

339 Table 1

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	163	39.951
	Male	245	60.049
Education	Bachelor's degree	229	56.127
	Doctorate	2	0.49
	High school degree or equivalent	70	17.157
	Less than a high school diploma	4	0.98
	Master's degree	102	25
	Other	1	0.245
	Income	\$20.000 - \$29.999	74
	\$30.000 - \$39.999	53	12.99
	\$40.000 - \$49.999	43	10.539
	\$50.000 - \$59.999	38	9.314
	\$60.000 - \$69.999	26	6.373
	\$70.000 - \$79.999	22	5.392
	\$80.000 - \$89.999	13	3.186
	\$90.000 ≥	45	11.029
	≤ \$19.999	94	23.039
Status	Employed full-time	238	58.333
	Employed part-time	61	14.951
	Retired	4	0.98
	Self-employed	34	8.333
	Student	44	10.784

Unable to work	3	0.735
Unemployed	24	5.882
Total	408	100

341 *Note.* Author developed, 2022

342 **4. Results**

343 We analysed the proposed theoretical model using partial least squares structural
344 equation modelling (PLS-SEM). The R environment was used in the study, based on the
345 Lavaan extension. This method allowed to analyse relationships between several dependent
346 and independent variables in one model. Analysis of the results was carried out in 2 stages. To
347 improve the credibility of the obtained results, we used bootstrapping. In the analysis, the
348 number of re-samples was 5,000. The use of bootstrapping with a small number of items (18)
349 and a 3-level model indicates that the number of more than 200 respondents was sufficient for
350 the analysis.

351 First, we performed an assessment of reliability and validity regarding the measurement
352 model, and secondly, an assessment of the structural model and testing hypotheses. The
353 constructs are available in table 2. Assessment of the measurement model was based on
354 confirmatory factor analysis and reliability assessment, internal consistency and convergent as
355 well as discriminant validity. Evaluation of the variables was primarily based on loading value.
356 The specified cut-off value was 0.7. In the case of one variable - EoE3, the obtained value was
357 0.469, therefore, the values were recalculated. In all cases, the achieved value exceeded 0.7,
358 being within the range of 0.773-.909, surpassing the value of the analysed variability at the
359 level of 44.9% with meets Harman's one-factor test for common method bias. Detailed values
360 are presented in Table 3. To evaluate internal consistency, we analysed composite reliability
361 and Cronbach's alpha for each of the constructs . All variables met the criteria of being > 0.7.
362 They were in the range suitable for CR 0.78-0.92, and for Cronbach's alpha 0.76-0.92.
363 Convergence validity evaluation was used to measure average variance extracted (AVE),
364 which showed that the variance shared between a construct and its measures for all variables
365 met the required level. The AVE values for each variable exceeded the recommended level of
366 0.5 and ranged from 0.55-0.75.

367 Table 2

SPC	simulated physical control
EE	environmental embedding
QMI	quality of mental imagery
PL	product liking
EOE	ease of evaluation
PI	purchase intention

369 *Note.* Author developed, 2022

370 Table 3

371 *Confirmatory factor analysis*

Construct	Item	Loading	p value	Cronbach's	CR	AVE
α						
QMI	QMI1	0.78	***	0.87	0.87	0.63
	QMI2	0.77	***			
	QMI3	0.82	***			
	QMI4	0.81	***			
SPC	SPC1	0.89	***	0.90	0.90	0.75
	SPC2	0.89	***			
	SPC3	0.82	***			
EOE	EOE1	0.91	***	0.76	0.78	0.55
	EOE2	0.76	***			
	EOE3	0.53	***			
EE	EE1	0.85	***	0.85	0.85	0.75
	EE2	0.88	***			
PL	PL1	0.83	***	0.89	0.88	0.72

	PL2	0.86	***			
	PL3	0.85	***			
PI	PI1	0.84	***	0.92	0.92	0.74
	PI2	0.85	***			
	PI3	0.87	***			

372 *Note.* * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Author developed, 2022

373 The HTMT ratio of correlations was used to assess discriminant validity. As shown in
374 Table 4, the HTMT ratios of the correlation for each construct did not exceed 0.9 and it should
375 be stated that these 2 constructs were not the same.

376 Table 4

377 *Discriminant validity*

	EE	SPC	QMI	EOE	PL	PI
EE	1.00					
SPC	0.50	1.00				
QMI	0.72	0.36	1.00			
EOE	0.89	0.46	0.83	1.00		
PL	0.46	0.84	0.36	0.36	1.00	
PI	0.47	0.78	0.41	0.42	0.85	1.00

378 *Note.* Author developed, 2022

379 Various measures were used to evaluate the model, as recommended by Schumacker
380 and Lomax (1996). Therefore, the model was tested using 3 types of fit indices: absolute,
381 parsimonious and incremental fit measure. All the obtained fit indices met the suggested
382 ranges, i.e. CMIN/df = 1.99, RMSEA = 0.049, GFI = 0.93, CFI = 0.98 and NFI = 0.95 (Hair et
383 al., 2014) also meet the requirements, which allows us to assume that the proposed model is
384 well-suited and permits evaluation analysis in accordance with the proposed hypotheses.

385 Table 5 contains the results of the SEM analysis and figure 3 depicts the same with our
386 research model. In the case of the EOE variable, the study revealed the influence of all
387 independent variables: EE (b = 0.56, $p < 0.001$), SPC (b = 0.33, $p < 0.001$), and QMI (b = 0.13,
388 $p < 0.01$). On this basis, it can be assumed that hypotheses H1, H2 and H7 have been confirmed.

389 The obtained R^2 value for QMI was 0.26 and it was determined by EE ($b = 0.59, p < 0.001$)
 390 which confirms H6, but in relation to H5, the study does not confirm the influence of SPC (b
 391 $= 0.01, ns$).

392 Subsequently, the influence of independent variables on PL was analysed. In the case
 393 of SPC and EE, the values were not statistically significant, which indicates that it is not
 394 possible to adopt the H3 and H4 hypotheses based on the collected empirical material. In the
 395 case of QMI, this influence was $b = 0.5, p < 0.001$, which confirms hypothesis H8. The overall
 396 R^2 level for PL was 0.73, while the R^2 value for PI was at 0.78 level. This analysis allowed us
 397 to reveal that both PL and EOE had a statistically significant influence on PI and were $b = 0.79,$
 398 $p < 0.001$ for PL and $b = 0.15, p < 0.001$, respectively. This confirms the adopted hypotheses H9
 399 and H10.

400 Additionally, for the analyzed overall SEM model, a mediation analysis was performed
 401 to assess the importance of QMI in a better understanding of the mechanisms of AR influence.
 402 As the relationship between SPC and QMI turned out to be negligible and statistically
 403 insignificant, the focus was on EE as an independent variable. Two mediation analyzes were
 404 conducted. In the first case, results of the test of the meditational model of QMI as a mediator
 405 of the relationship between EE and PL indicated that whilst the total effect was significant (b
 406 $= 0.368, p < .001$), the direct effect was not ($b = .036, p = .335$). QMI fully mediated the
 407 relationship between EE and PL. In the case of the QMI mediation effect in the relation between
 408 EE and EOE, the results indicate partial mediation, reaching a total effect of $b = 0.943, p < .001$
 409 with a statistically significant direct effect ($b = 0.862, p < .001$) and a statistically significant
 410 indirect effect $b = 0.073, p = .004$

411 Table 5.

412 *Results of SEM*

Endogenous Variable	Exogenous Variable	Beta	B	SE	p-value	CI lower	CI upper
EOE	EE	0.56	0.61	0.07	***	0.47	0.75
EOE	SPC	0.33	0.29	0.05	***	0.19	0.39
EOE	QMI	0.13	0.19	0.06	**	0.07	0.31
QMI	SPC	0.01	0.01	0.05	<i>ns</i>	-0.08	0.10

QMI	EE	0.50	0.36	0.06	***	0.24	0.48
PL	EE	-0.02	-0.02	0.05	ns	-0.12	0.08
PL	SPC	0.08	0.05	0.04	ns	-0.02	0.12
PL	QMI	0.83	0.89	0.06	***	0.76	1.02
PI	PL	0.79	0.88	0.06	***	0.76	0.99
PI	EOE	0.15	0.12	0.03	***	0.06	0,18

413 *Note.* * ns – not significant ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.00$. Author developed, 2022

414 *Figure 3.* Results of study. Author developed, 2022

415

416 5. Discussion

417 Our research discovered that SPC exerted a direct, albeit weak positive influence on
 418 EOE. This is in line with the research of Jiang and Benbasat (2004) who discovered that
 419 perceived diagnosticity, which is the degree to which a consumer believes the shopping
 420 experience is helpful to evaluate a product tended to increase if the user possessed functional
 421 control of an electronic interface. EE was also discovered to have a positive influence on EOE,
 422 allowing us to produce that the AR's ability to embed a product into a respondent's local
 423 environment, enabled them to link abstract "facts" with a real-time context, to reduce

424 evaluation difficulties. What was interesting and need further perusal, however, was the
425 rejection of H5 in which we hypothesized that SPC would have a positive influence on QMI.
426 This counters extant AR research of Park and Yoo (2020) who discovered the controllability
427 of products to have positively influenced the QMI. We believe the reason this might be is as
428 the product on which the respondents exerted SPC was a food product, unlike in the research
429 of Park and Yoo (2020) where a female group of respondents used a makeup cosmetic app.
430 With food, one does not need to exert as much SPC as one would when applying cosmetics
431 using AR considering the food product is placed in the environment in front of them. The
432 results might also be as such considering that food is a one-time purchase that can be consumed
433 only once, unlike makeup which is a multi-use product. It might also be that the users were
434 familiar with the product we presented in AR, thereby not needing any interaction with the
435 object to create a mental image of it. Another reason might have been that respondents who are
436 looking to purchase a mass-produced product such as a chair would expect the 3D object in
437 their environment to be identical to the actual product, and would therefore exert more SPC,
438 whereas with food this is not possible. In line with this thinking, the results might have been
439 different had we exposed the respondents to exotic food they are not familiar with. This
440 however is conjecture at best and will be included in our future research agenda, further on.
441 We also confirmed that EE had a positive influence on the QMI, further confirming AR's
442 ability to assist with the generation stage of mental imagery, and even the memory intensive
443 process of maintaining it, as the respondents were able to simply embed a 3D model of a
444 product in their backdrop. Such a finding is important as the generation stage is the first step
445 of mental imagery, and the second stage: transformation, can only then improve upon it. A
446 surprising turn of events, however, was the rejection of the hypothesis where QMI was
447 expected to positively influence EOE. This finding counter extant research which highlights
448 the importance of mental imagery to pre-consumption product evaluations and merits further
449 investigation.

450 We also discovered that our hypotheses in which we posited that SPC and EE would
451 positively influence PL has been rejected. This counters extant research of Kowalczyk et al.
452 (2021), who discovered the ability to interact with or exert SPC on AR products to have
453 influenced PL positively. We believe that this discrepancy might lie in the type of product
454 presented as the respondents in the work of Kowalczyk et al. (2021) exerted SPC on a desk
455 chair, which is essentially a product which one needs to move around and place in a correct
456 background unlike with a food product. Another reason might be that AR-driven multisensory

457 features such as SPC and EE are not novel anymore, thanks to the existence of AR apps
458 introduced by those such as IKEA, L’Oreal, Sephora, Snapchat filters, and Instagram, or even
459 games such as Pokémon GO. Our work also found QMI to have had a strong positive influence
460 on PL, and adds to extant research on the positive impact of mental imagery on product
461 attitudes.

462 What was interesting, however, was the findings we obtained after conducting a
463 mediation analysis to assess the importance of QMI to better understand the mechanisms of
464 AR influence. Considering the negligible and statistically insignificant relationship between
465 SPC and QMI, we opted to use EE as the independent variable. Through it, we discovered a
466 partial mediation when QMI was added as a mediator between EE and EOE with a statistically
467 significant direct effect and a statistically significant indirect effect. What proved to be
468 interesting was our discovery of a total mediation between EE and PL when QMI was
469 introduced as a mediator. Considering this, we can establish that in the food domain, QMI
470 created an indirect effect between EE and PL, which is a significant finding.

471 The second part of our third research aim, which attempted to discover how EOE and
472 PL influence PI confirmed both hypothesis statements. It is however worth mentioning that the
473 relationship between EOE and PI was rather weak, and we attribute this to factors outside the
474 control of this study such as degree of hunger while participating or special dietary preferences
475 (a respondent opting for a non-meat lifestyle would not like a chicken meal). The simple
476 conclusion from this finding is that consumers who experienced the product in AR were able
477 to make a fast decision due to EOE and simply chose not to move forward with a purchase.
478 With this line of reasoning, we would expect to have discovered different results had there been
479 a range of products to choose from on our website or had we asked further questions on the
480 degree of hunger or dietary preferences as EOE at present resembles a moderator than a factor
481 with a significant positive impact on PI. The influence from PL to PI was also strong, allowing
482 us to highlight the usefulness of EE and QMI in driving an affective response such as PL which
483 in turn affects a behavioral response such as PI.

484 **6.0 Conclusion**

485 The aims of this research paper were threefold: to contribute to reducing the gap of food
486 and AR research in the field of consumer behaviour, to understand how food presented in AR
487 impacts the EOE of products and further the research on how AR-induced affective (EOE, PL)

488 and cognitive (QMI) psychological mechanisms can drive behavioural responses. We consider
489 all three to have been achieved and present our contributions to theory and practice below.

490 **6.1 Theoretical contributions**

491 Considering the dearth of AR research and consumer behavior in the food domain, we
492 consider ours to be a welcome addition and a timely one as the global food delivery market is
493 growing in exponential bounds. Our first theoretical contribution, therefore, is our research
494 focus on the EOE of the food product, a previously untested affective construct in the food
495 domain, and one we discovered was influenced by SPC and EE. The inclusion of such a
496 construct we believe is an important one considering the effects of increased evaluation
497 difficulties such as confusion and its corresponding negative behavioral outputs. The second is
498 our inclusion of the cognitive construct QMI which we discovered contradicted previous AR
499 research (Park & Yoo, 2020) as SPC was found to not influence it. We posit that this might be
500 due to the nature of the product as respondents might not need to interact or rather play with
501 their food once the product is embedded in their environment. This would not be the case with
502 extant research which ours contradict as the product therein was a makeup app which a
503 respondent would need to interact with for it to serve its intended purpose. The same can be
504 said if the object in question was an item of living room furniture as the respondent would need
505 to control and exert SPC on the 3D model that was embedded into their environment to observe
506 how it would look in a certain part of their living room. The third is our discovery of the lack
507 of influence on PL from both SPC and EE, which contracts the previous AR research of
508 Kowalczyk et al. (2021), who discovered the ability to interact with or exert SPC on AR
509 products to have influenced PL positively. We posit that this might be caused by the nature of
510 the product again as extant research showcased a furniture product that one would consider
511 identical to the actual product whereas one might be more hesitant with food as items on the
512 menu are rarely identical to the end product. Our fourth contribution is the discovery of a total
513 mediation between EE and PL with QMI as the mediator. This allows us to posit QMI as a
514 cognitive construct responsible for creating an indirect effect between EE and PL and is an
515 important contribution to the extant literature on AR-driven mental imagery and food
516 preferences. The fifth contribution is our discovery of how EOE did not lead to PI, contrary to
517 extant literature that posits that positive affective states translate to behavioral effects. The
518 simple conclusion from this finding is that consumers who experienced the product in AR were

519 able to make a fast decision due to EOE and simply chose not to move forward with a purchase.
520 We attribute this to personal attributes such as dietary preferences (vegan, non-vegan) or even
521 degree of hunger, factors that are incidentally not relevant when evaluating products such as
522 makeup or chairs but are relevant to food. With this line of reasoning, we would expect to have
523 discovered different results had there been a range of products to choose from on our website,
524 as EOE at present resembles a moderator than a factor with a significant positive impact on PI.
525 Considering the dearth of AR research in the food domain, we posit our discovery of a positive
526 influence from PL to PI, as the fifth theoretical contribution.

527 Another output of this research that we dare say could be considered a theoretical
528 contribution is that we have taken heed of the call for more generalizable research on areas
529 such as food from Caboni and Pizzichini (2022). It was also conducted with respondents who
530 were not all students, outside controlled laboratory conditions, heeding the call for results
531 validated from real users from AR researchers such as H. K. Song et al. (2020), Watson et al.
532 (2020) and Xu et al. (2020). Our research on AR's impact on QMI, EOE, PL and PI also
533 contributes to extant research helping unravel decision complexity, as recommended in the
534 future research agenda of the AR literature review of Hilken et al. (2018)

535 **6.2 Practical contributions**

536 Considering our findings, product presentation using AR can help consumers evaluate
537 between products (EOE) thanks to their ability to interact (SPC) and embed the product in their
538 local environment (EE). This is beneficial as consumers can make decisions faster without
539 negative emotions associated with overwhelming product choices found on an online menu.
540 We believe this finding can also prove to be useful for restaurants as their patrons can
541 experience food products and decide, without having to consult the staff, to consider the portion
542 size or the aesthetics of the product. Such product presentation we believe would be even more
543 important if the food was of exotic nature that the patrons are not familiar with. For food
544 retailers, either online or physical, this might mean higher chances of the patrons liking the
545 food, increase repurchase intentions or even electronic word-of-mouth marketing. Our
546 discovery of QMI's ability to create a positive indirect effect between EE and PL is also useful
547 information for retailers, as product presentation with AR means that consumers need not
548 expend any mental efforts to create mental imagery as EE does it for them and this, in turn, led

549 to PL. This PL we discovered has a strong influence on PI, which incidentally is a favorable
550 behavioral response for food retailers.

551 Considering the positive cognitive, affective and behavioral responses we observed as
552 a result of AR product presentations, we believe that food retailers should integrate AR into
553 their retail channels as it benefits both the consumers and the retailers themselves. Doing so is
554 no longer reserved for retailers with sizable capital as WebAR is a very effective method of
555 providing an AR experience to consumers and deserves close consideration due to its cost-
556 effectiveness when compared to the cost of app development. Such WebAR experiences, we
557 believe, will also tend to be more attractive to consumers as they need not download apps that
558 raise privacy concerns, take up memory on their mobile devices, and are costly to download
559 from the Internet and install.

560 **6.3 Limitations and future research**

561 Despite our best attempts to minimise the limitations encountered in this study, there
562 are some that we believe are worth highlighting. The first is that our respondents were English-
563 speaking, digital natives, who were proficient in the usage of Internet-connected mobile
564 devices, with previous experience in online shopping. Notwithstanding our strong faith in both
565 the short- and long-term benefits of using AR in product presentation for consumers and
566 retailers, we also realise that it might not be the best option for those who are not digitally
567 savvy. It is also worth mentioning that our research was only focused on the visual mental
568 imagery of AR and no other sensory modalities such as those auditory, olfactory, gustatory, or
569 tactile. There is, however, space for including auditory and tactile sensory modalities in future
570 research, to evaluate whether they have an impact on the affective and cognitive behaviours of
571 consumers. We also believe that the results of our research were influenced by the degree of
572 hunger respondents displayed, as it is fair to assume that a respondent who just had dinner,
573 would not be as enthusiastic about the purchase intention of another plate of food. Dietary
574 restrictions were also considered to have been a limitation in this research as a respondent who
575 steers clear of meat would not be as keen or display PL towards a dish such as a chicken meal.

576 Since AR is now a fast-maturing technology, easily accessible thanks to WebAR, we
577 believe there is scope for expanding consumer behavior research in the food domain.
578 Considering EOE is an important construct for prepurchase evaluations, we urge future
579 researchers to investigate more into its impact on behavioral responses. Considering our

580 research did not evaluate the general digital savviness of our respondents, it might also be
581 interesting to further this research to observe whether factors such as media novelty or previous
582 exposure to AR might have an impact on the results. It is also worth considering whether
583 research using our model but with a product such as furniture would yield different findings to
584 ours as we posited that our findings that contradicted extant research were due to the object
585 being a food product. Another interesting avenue of research would be how the experience of
586 products in AR might affect the perceived price and quality of the product (including taste).
587 Future researchers may also want to investigate whether existing attitudes, such as like/dislike
588 towards certain food items, are more accentuated or subdued after an experience with AR
589 product presentations. We also consider a further investigation of how hardware factors, i.e.
590 pixel density of the screen, could play an important role in the quality of the 3D model
591 experienced by the respondents and its impact on behaviours. Finally, we urge researchers to
592 look for partnerships with organisations that are actively using AR to present their products to
593 measure their impact on sales, not remaining limited to purchase intention alone.

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598 **Conflicts of Interest**

599 The authors declare no conflict of interest

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796 **Appendix**

797 **Environmental embedding** (Song et al., 2019)

798 I was able to see how the product looked in my environment.

799 I felt like I had the product very close to me

800 **Simulated physical control** (Song et al., 2019)

801 While I was using this augmented reality service, I was able to move the product around

802 The product was easy to control

803 I had physical control over the product.

804 **Quality of mental imagery** (Park & Yoo, 2020)

805 Overall, the images that came to mind while I used the AR were ...

806 Very dull – Very sharp

807 Very weak – Very intense

808 Very unclear – Very clear

809 Very vague – Very vivid

810 **Ease of evaluation** (McDougall, 1987)

811 Picking the product I would like is an easy decision for me to make, thanks to AR

812 I wouldn't spend much time making a decision on the product I like, thanks to AR

813 I'd want a lot of information before making a decision on the product I like

814 **Product liking** (Kowalczyk et al., 2021)

815 Very bad - Very good

816 Very unpleasant – Very pleasant

817 Not likable at all – Very likable

818 **Purchase intention** (Kowalczyk et al., 2021)

819 Not at all certain - Very certain

- 820 Highly unlikely - Highly likely
- 821 Definitely improbable – Definitely probable
- 822 It is highly unlikely - It is highly likely